
Green CosmIn

“Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics”

Data Management Plan

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General project information

Project Acronym	GreenCosmIn
Project number	101131346
Project Title	Green chemistry and biotechnology approaches for the development of nature-based cosmetics
Call	HORIZON-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Coordinator	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)
Project starting date	1 March 2024
Project duration	48 months

GreenCosmIn list of partners

No	Name	Short name	Role	Country
1	NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NKUA	COO	EL
2	UNIVERSITE DE REIMS CHAMPAGNE-ARDENNE	URCA	BEN	FR
3	UNIVERSITE D'ORLEANS	UORL	BEN	FR
4	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	TUM	BEN	DE
5	UNIwersytet Medyczny w Lublinie	MUL	BEN	PL
6	WYŻSZA SZKOŁA INFORMATYKI I ZARZĄDZANIA Z SIEDZIBĄ W RZESZOWIE	UITM	BEN	PL
7	FACULTE DES SCIENCES DE SFAX	FSS	BEN	TN
8	PHARMAGNOSE VIOTECHNOLOGIKI ANONYMI ETAIERIA	PhG	BEN	EL
9	ADSI-AUSTRIAN DRUG SCREENING INSTITUTE GMBH	ADSI	BEN	AT
10	PHYTOWELT GREENTECHNOLOGIES GMBH	PHY	BEN	DE
11	NAT EXPLORE	NATEX	BEN	FR
12	LE STUDIUM, AGENCE REGIONALE DE RECHERCHE ET D'ACCEUIL INTERNATIONAL DE CHERCHEURS ASSOCIES	STU	BEN	FR
13	UNIVERSITE DE LA POLYNESIE FRANCAISE	UPF	BEN	PF
14	MONGOLIAN NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	MNUMS	AP	MN

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1. Data Summary

Purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the GreenCosmIn project

The GreenCosmIn project will be carried out by a consortium of partners from different sectors and aims at the development of scientific methods that will be used for the recognition of valuable natural products and plant extracts to be used in the cosmetic industry.

The project will be generating research data during the conducted experiments that include instrumental data, laboratory protocols, sample descriptions, scale-up methods, formulations and others, to:

- improve the workflow of the project,
- demonstrate and transparently communicate the results and activities of the GreenCosmIn project,
- disseminate the key outputs in a clear and inclusive way,
- evaluate the effectiveness of the activities and later - the understanding of the project results by all stakeholders (academia, industry, public and policy makers).

Issues arising from data re-use

The datasets generated within the GreenCosmIn project includes new research data produced in the consortium. The data will be maintained and organized for possible future research projects.

Types and formats of data that the project will generate or re-use

The described dataset of the GreencosmIn project, outlined in this DMP will be new experimental data in the field of pharmacognosy, pharmacy, analytical chemistry, biotechnology, pharmaceutical technology, molecular biology, pharmacology, toxicology and related fields.

Data will include the information recorded during the performed experiments and also other exploitation and dissemination material generated from the realization of the project scientific topics.

More specifically data will be produced by research and exploitation/ dissemination activities of GreenCosmIn project partners and will comprise curated (processed) data of experiments and exploitation/ dissemination material.

Formats will comprise but are not limited to:

*.docx, *.xlsx, *.pptx, *.pdf, *.txt, *.csv (ASCII or Unicode), *.rtf, *.htm, *.html, *.xml, *.php, *.asp, *.jpg, *.jpeg, *.jpe, *.bmp, *.dib, *.gif, *.png, *.tiff, *.tga, *.psd, *.ai, *.odi, *.indd

File collection containing a large number of files or subfolders may be published when compressed to *.rar or *.zip files.

Expected data size generated within the GreenCosmIn project

The average size of one file is from 100 kB to 1 GB depending on the type of instrumentation used. Curated (processed) data sets can also vastly differ in size, however the maximum per dataset is expected to be within a range of 10-50 GB.

Origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used

Data will be produced at all sites of GreenCosmIn project partners and related research facilities as stated in the Grant Agreement.

Data utility outside the GreenCosmIn project

Datasets generated in the framework of GreenCosmIn project might be of interest for diverse stakeholders, i.e., researchers, pharmaceutical and cosmetics industry managers, decision makers, including public and private health institutions, as well as governmental authorities. More specifically, cosmetic and pharma industry are relevant to the research outcomes of GreenCosmIn as well as public and non-public health organisations and institutes.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data identification by a persistent identifier

The GreenCosmIn project will use an internationally accepted file format for effective sharing, re-use, and preservation of data. All data will be accompanied by appropriate data documentation (including names, labels, descriptions of variables, explanations of any codes or classification schemes, descriptions of derived data and what analyses or algorithms were used). Further, data will be accompanied by scientifically widely accepted persistent identified (PID) “Digital Object Identifier” (DOI) or patent identification numbers wherever applicable (e.g., scientific publications).

Metadata generated within the GreenCosmIn project

Uploading at Zenodo for datasets provides the opportunity to link data uploaded to metadata such as DOI, keywords, publishing date, related identifiers, alternate identifiers, linkage to related communities, licensing agreements and version tracking. Keywords will be provided wherever applicable for generated metadata. Finally, metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed.

2.2. Making data accessible

Data repository

Data created within the framework of the GreenCosmIn project will be stored in the open repository Zenodo. Also, the collected data will be stored in the clouds of the Partner Institutions according to the elaborated policies, as listed in the table in section 7.

Arrangements concerning the identified repository where the data will be deposited and partner security policies

Each partner has their own data security policies and procedures, all have provided statements and evidence of compliance with ISO 27001:2013 or equivalent security standards as shown in Section 7. Further, Zenodo has been specifically designed through OpenAIRE to allow open access to the project data. The metadata will be openly available under CC-BY license, unless they fall under the commercial interests of industry partners. The project's intellectual property committee (IPC) in collaboration with the Executive Board (EB) will resolve all issues related to data availability.

Digital object identifiers

All data deposited at Zenodo repository will be assigned to identifiers and automatically resolved to a digital object by Zenodo wherever applicable.

Data availability and restricted access conditions

GreenCosmIn will use the Zenodo open repository. The data will be first kept closed, and after the publication of original articles, the supplementary data and raw files will be opened. However, certain datasets might require an embargo applied for a certain period of time. The Intellectual Property Committee (IPC) in collaboration with the Executive Board (EB) should be responsible for monitoring the procedure. This will include data within an ongoing patenting process. Specifically, an embargo is required since all openly available, thus published data is considered prior art, most specifically for patent law but also in scientific publishing processes.

Also, the information that is crucial for the industrial partners for the preparation of the final formulations will not be shared, in contrast to the procedures and results of general character that can be useful for other stakeholders from outside the project consortium.

Embargo period for the protection of intellectual property within the GreenCosmIn project

Wherever needed, data will be subjected to a publication embargo in order to give partners the opportunity to publish and/ or patent authentic data that has not been publicly available prior to patent priority date or publication date. This is mandatory in any publishing or patenting process. The embargo duration can vary depending on the review duration and it is hardly possible to generalize this due to drastic differences in review speed. However, a minimum of 6-month embargo starting from the submission date will be necessary. The GreenCosmIn consortium will try to ensure timely open access to published/ patented data. It should be noted that data might be kept closed due to partners legitimate interests, which is described in the above section. Whenever necessary, the project's Intellectual Property Committee (IPC) in collaboration with the

Executive Board (EB) will convene to decide on specific details for protection of intellectual property generated within the project.

Data accessibility through a free and standardized access protocol

GreenCosmIn will provide all data designated to be openly available via a free and standardized access protocol. The consortium will therefore choose the internet protocol, respectively represented by Zenodo repository homepage, hosted by CERN.

Access to the generated data whenever restrictions apply

Data that will be publicly available will be disclosed on the Zenodo platform, hence restrictions regarding data accessibility should not apply.

Identity of the person accessing the data

Not applicable for open access data sets.

Data access committee

There is no need for an establishment of a data access committee within the GreenCosmIn project.

Metadata availability

Metadata will be openly available and is subject to the license under which the data objects were deposited. CC-BY License will be used, unless otherwise agreed to use a different one.

Data and metadata availability during and beyond the GreenCosmIn project

GreenCosmIn partners will use Zenodo for permanent storage of openly accessible (meta-) data. Zenodo is hosted by CERN for at least the next 20 years for which a succession plan is in place in case CERN repository closes thus long-term accessibility is assured.

Possible use of specialized software for data sharing

The GreenCosmIn project will provide data mostly in standard data formats (e.g. *.pdf, *.docx, *.txt etc.).

2.3. Making data interoperable

Regarding the methodologies that the GreenCosmIn project will employ to make data interoperable, Zenodo will be the repository of choice. GreenCosmIn will follow metadata vocabulary, standards, formats, and methodologies according to standards in the field.

In case it is unavoidable that the project uses uncommon data or generates project specific ontologies or vocabularies, the partners will provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies and/or openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them.

Finally, the GreenCosmIn project data will include, wherever necessary, qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research).

2.4. Increase data re-use

Documentation required to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)

Readme files will be generated with information on i.a., methodology, variable definitions, units of measurements.

Data availability in public domains, data licenses in line with the Grant Agreement

The GreenCosmIn project will use Zenodo (hosted by CERN for at least the next 20 years for which a succession plan is in place in case CERN repository closes). Use and re-use is subject to the license under which the data objects were deposited. CC-BY License will be used, unless otherwise agreed to use a different one.

Data usage by third parties after the end of the project

Wherever applicable data will be stored in Zenodo for long-term open-access storage, if not otherwise agreed on (e.g., by embargo on data or partners legitimate interests).

Data documentation using the appropriate standards

The provided data will be stored using Zenodo, whereby Zenodo provides versioning and DOI for all uploaded data and thus provenance of data can be assured.

Data quality assurance processes

Quality assurance of provided data will be conducted by the data management responsible person for each consortium partner. Quality assurance generally takes place before the data will be made publicly available. The following measures are undertaken:

- Curated datasets ready for upload will to be checked by the responsible data manager of each partner and signed for completeness. This step needs to be documented in the version tracking section or accompanying readme files.
- Data without a definite document object identifier (DOI) will be considered as provisional and will remain in “draft” mode until this information is provided
- After publishing of data, no changes can be made without the consent of the project coordinator
- All uploaded data need to have trackable versioning.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

3. Other research outputs

Management of other research outputs (digital - e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc. or physical - e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.) that may be generated or re-used throughout the GreenCosmIn project.

The GreenCosmIn project will generate process specific datasets including but not limited to validated chromatographic methods, solvent compositions suitable for the fractionation of extracts, bioactivity assay conditions, libraries of metabolites, specification for scale up targets as well as all dissemination and exploitation targets. These data sets will be detailed in tabular and graphical forms, which will be used by the project consortium and for some of them – they will be available in public under standardized data formats and treated equivalently to experimental data sets outlines above.

Management, sharing and re-use of research outputs based on the FAIR principles

The consortium will attempt to treat all datasets pertaining to research outputs equally to any experimental open access data as detailed above. However, in the case of research outputs directly linked to intellectual property rights of participating institutions, datasets will be treated as sensitive and not made publicly available (e.g. composition of the final formulation, processes for the large-scale production of bioactive compounds etc.). In these cases, other data, such as laboratory protocols, analytical method details and information relevant to a wider range of plant species, will be opened to the scientific community and industry stakeholders. Whenever necessary, the project’s Intellectual Property Committee (IPC) in collaboration with the Executive Board (EB) will convene to decide on specific details for protection of intellectual property generated within the project.

4. Allocation of resources

Costs for making data or other research outputs FAIR in the GreenCosmIn project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)

Open access publication costs and conference participation fees are the only foreseeable costs other than effort, associated with data management of the GreenCosmIn project.

Costs directly related to the e.g., publication costs as well as personnel costs will be directly covered by the GreenCosmIn grant. Additionally, costs may be partly covered by other funding sources (e.g. scholarships, national funds etc.) that fully comply with the data management values and principles of Horizon Europe.

Persons responsible for data management in the GreenCosmIn project

Organization	Data Management Person
NKUA	Prof. Maria Halabalaki
URCA	Prof. Jean-Hugues Renault
UO-ICOA	Prof. David da Silva
TUM	Prof. Thomas Brueck
MUL	Prof. Wirginia Kukuła-Koch
UITM	Prof. Katarzyna Gawel-Bęben
UPF	Prof. Phila Bianchini-Raharivelomanana
FSS	Prof. Noureddine Allouche
PhG	Mr. Alkis Skaltsounis
ADSI	Dr. Thomas Jakschitz
NATEX	Dr. Jane Hubert
PHY	Dr. Philipp Wuthenow
STU	Dr. Sophie Gabillet
MNUMS	Prof. Daariimaa Khurelbat

Insurance of long-term data preservation with the use of necessary resources

Zenodo is hosted by CERN for at least the next 20 years for which a succession plan is in place in case CERN repository closes thus long-term accessibility is assured.

5. Data security

Provisions in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)

Security measures for the uploaded data are those of the repository where they reside. Thus, as a precaution measure, only trusted repositories, such as Zenodo, will be used.

Safe data storage in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation

As stated in one of the paragraphs above, data will be stored using Zenodo, in a PostgreSQL instance hosted on CERN's database infrastructure with a 12-hour backup cycle for at least the next 20 years for which a succession plan is in place in case CERN repository closes thus long-term accessibility is assured.

The following security mechanisms will be used: physical servers at CERN, HTTPS, encrypted passwords, tokens.

6. Ethics

Ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing

Project GreenCosmIn will be managed in compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law in the implementation of research and innovation activities. Any ethical concerns raised by those activities will be handled following rigorously the recommendations provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines.

GreenCosmIn is based on the application of green chemistry and biotechnology principles for the discovery of natural ingredients to be used in cosmetic formulations. In order to achieve this goal, extraction of plant material will be performed. The plant material to be used will not originate from protected areas nor from endangered taxa.

GreenCosmIn has one associated partner from low-income countries, namely MNUMS from Mongolia. Several benefit-sharing actions have been envisaged for the efficient collaboration and especially know-how transfer from more advanced partners from EU Member States to the economically vulnerable associated partner. MNUMS will participate with extensive secondments of researchers to companies and research institutes in order to be trained in contemporary natural product chemistry techniques (automated extraction, isolation, structural identification, bioactivity evaluation, metabolomics and chemometrics). In addition, it will participate in workshops, summer schools, seminars, and will have the opportunity to return to their host institution with enhanced expertise on their field.

GreenCosmIn activities will be in complete accordance with National/International laws and treaties (community ethics, protection of biodiversity, Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-sharing, UN Convention on Biological Diversity, legislation on Natura 200 network, and for French Polynesia the work will be carried out in conformity with the regulatory devices set up by French Polynesia, within the framework of its environmental code and the ABS system).

Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation

An establishment of an informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation is not applicable for the GreenCosmIn project.

7. Other issues

National/ funder/ sectorial/departmental procedures for data management

GreenCosmin will be using also other procedures for data management that were elaborated in the partnering institutions.

NKUA	<p>From 25.5.2018, the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679, also known as GDPR, applies, which strengthens the framework of the protection of data subjects with regard to the processing of personal data in the European Union. With respect to personal data, NKUA complies with the GDPR in the context of its activity and purpose and takes the prescribed technical and organizational measures for the effective protection of personal data, according to the provisions of the GDPR and Greek legislation by extension. The Network Operation and Management Center (KLEIDI) is an independent organizational unit of the University of Athens, with the aim of providing IT and communications services to members of the academic community, staff and students. KLEIDI supports more than 80,000 members of the academic community by offering innovative online services and digital media to support collaboration, communication and education.</p>
URCA	<p>With respect to personal data, URCA complies with the GDPR in the context of its activity and purpose and takes the prescribed technical and organizational measures for the effective protection of personal data, according to the provisions of the GDPR and French legislation by extension.</p> <p>Data repository from GCI is considered as an Individual Data Management Plan (IDMP). IDMP must detail the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type and origin of the data (e.g., collected or produced; observational, experimental, simulation data); - Method of collecting new data and/or the conditions for reusing pre-existing data - Data processing methods - Conditions for data storage and protection - Methods for data sharing at the end of the projects. <p>For IDMP, the national platform https://dmp.opidor.fr/ will be used.</p>
UO-ICOA	<p>As part of the file/data management policy of the UO-ICOA, which is a laboratory falling under the ZRR restrictive regime zones, the latter reinforces the protection framework for the data generated by separating and protecting sensitive data. Although the servers are private and accessible only from ICOA or via VPN for authorized persons via Windows Active Directory, the opening of data generated within the framework of the GreenCosmIn project will be implemented, excluding data whose disclosure is unjustified or impossible due to the protection of intellectual property rights or other legal provisions. Similarly to URCA, general approaches as described above could also be implemented.</p>
TUM	<p>Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) exchange solution Sync+Share should be applied for internal data</p>

	exchange. The exchange solution Sync+Share already being used on other EC funded projects is compliant with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (2016/679) and the additions in the Federal German Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz). LRZ and its employees are certified according to ISO 20000 and ISO 27001. Each partner has their own data security policies and procedures, all have provided statements and evidence of compliance with ISO 27001:2013 or equivalent security standards.
MUL	The project implementers undertake to respect intellectual property rights on the basis of the following acts of Polish law and in accordance with the UML Intellectual Property Management Regulations: Act on Copyright and Related Rights (February 4, 1994); Database Protection Act (July 27, 2001); Industrial Property Law (June 30, 2000); Act on Combating Unfair Competition (April 16, 1993), Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, The UML Rector's Order No. 9/2022 of 17-01-2022 on the introduction of the Policy for storing research data on the Disk Matrix of the Medical University of Lublin, the Policy for the Protection of Special Categories of Data deposited on the Disk Matrix of the Medical University of Lublin and the Procedure for allocating space on the Disk Matrix of the Medical University of Lublin), and by the Resolution No. CCXIV/2018 of the Senate of the Medical University of Lublin of October 24, 2018, excluding data whose disclosure is unjustified or impossible due to the protection of intellectual property rights or other legal provisions.
UITM	Not applicable.
UPF	DMP OPIDoR is recommended for UPF. DMP OPIDoR is a DMP writing assistance tool based on the open source DMPRoadmap code which was developed by the Digital Curation Center (DCC) and the University of California Curation Center (UC3). The source code for DMP OPIDoR is available on GitHub. DMP OPIDoR has been personalized for French researchers. The deposit of research data on the Research Data Gouv platforms (recherche.data.gouv.fr) or, on a global scale European, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is recommended as part of the UPF open science roadmap excluding data whose disclosure is unjustified or impossible due to the protection of intellectual property rights or other legal provisions in accordance with the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

FSS	Not applicable.
PhG	Not applicable.
ADSI	ADSI adheres to an internal data management policy that ensures adequate protection from data loss and theft. Data are stored on ADSI's own server infrastructure, which is mirrored internally and externally – in a different with a minimal delay. Critical data can moreover copied to cold storages on a regular basis to minimize the risk of successful ransomware attacks. ADSI is a wholly owned subsidiary of the University of Innsbruck and uses its IT infrastructure. Hence, the computers on ADSI's premises are protected by the firewall of the University of Innsbruck and operating system updates are deployed in an automated manner according to the policy by the University's IT department. User authorization is facilitated by means of Windows Active Directory. Access from outside the company's premises is only possible by means of a virtual private network with a two-factor secured login process. Details on how data and access are protected and regulated at the University of Innsbruck can be found on the website of the University's IT department (website in German only). Data to be shared within the framework of the GreenCosmIn project will be stored on a repository, which will be implemented for the consortium via Microsoft Teams. All relevant data will be provided in this repository excluding data whose disclosure is unjustified or impossible due to the protection of intellectual property rights or other legal provisions."
NATEX	Not applicable.
PHY	Not applicable.
STU	LE STUDIUM complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which came into force on 25 May 2018 to provide a better framework for data processing, and with the recommendations issued by the French Data Protection Authority (CNIL).
MNUMS	Project data management in Mongolian National University of Medical Sciences (MNUMS), is regulated by various legal frameworks, including the Law on Higher Education, the Law on Technology Transfer, and Regulations pertaining to copyright and related rights. Additionally, Government Resolution No. 282 of 2018 includes provisions that impact data management practices, particularly in the education and technology sectors. The rules of MNUMS, specifically clauses 3.4.1 and 3.4.7, offer detailed instructions on data handling, ensuring compliance with legal and ethical standards. These comprehensive regulations aim to protect data integrity, privacy, and security, while also promoting the

	responsible use of data in Mongolia's higher education and technology sectors.
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